

THE ARTIST'S IMAGE-LANDSCAPE-LITERARY SYNTHESIS

Mukhammadjonova Guzalkhan

Docent, PhD, Associate,
Fergana State University, UZBEKISTAN
+998916773086 guzalfayz@mail.ru
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5895072>

Annotation

The article discusses about an artistic interpretation of the image of a creative person – the literary synthesis of an artist. In the article we can see the illustration of the artistic and aesthetic function of the image of the artist's psyche throughout O'Henry's story "The Last Leaf".

Key words: image, artist's image, literary synthesis, composition, landscape, portrait.

Each literary work has small world of perfect composition. It has its own legitimacy, each of its small blessings has its own place and artistic-aesthetic function. Landscape and interior, which are part of the compositional means, are an important factor in giving the artist character, psyche, creative environment. "The writer realizes his ideological intention not only by the actions of the heroes, but also by depicting the natural landscapes that surround them. It aims to influence the reader through the image of the landscape, to cultivate in him a sense of beauty.

The term of "image" (fr. Paysage) is an important concept in both literature and art. The content and the essence are similar, but its creature ways are different. In one, the landscape of nature is created with using words, in the other it is done in colors, dyes, painter's brush. Both of them contains full of light and color, the color of nature, allegory, and aesthetic effect. In fiction, the landscape conveys the place, time (seasons) through reality within characters' feelings, psychology, mood and symbolic-philosophical meaning.

"The landscape is based on a real philosophical foundation. Since man lives side by side with natural phenomena in the bosom of nature, it is inevitable that a work of art will be incomplete and simple without any degree of depiction of natural phenomena. In addition, the most important thing is that the landscape in the work of art, the depiction of natural phenomena gives a special dimension to the events of the work - the celestial scale [2.29]. In the works depicting the image of the artist, we can find interpretations of the landscape typical of artistic synthesis.

The story of "Last leaf" by O'Henry is a work which illustrates the life of Eastern art's representatives. Besides, The work is also significant in that it is an

example of art depicting the image of women artists, which is also rare in Western literature and almost not reflected in Uzbek literature. Three of the four characters in the story are artist images. The exhibition, which began with a landscape painting, continues with a portrait of the heroes. From the lines of the landscape, the lifestyle of the artists becomes clear. Like the "narrow streets" in which they live, the paths of life of artists also crosses and connects. The fact that the collector of the money from the shop could not collect a penny for the purchased paper and cotton fabric and it is a clear indication of the social status of this street and the artists living in it. The play depicts the creative environment and the creative process on the example of the images of Sue, Johnsy, Berman. The human qualities of Sue and Berman are revealed in the case of Johnny's pneumonia. Within the great possibilities of the small genre, the universal eternal theme of life and death, the love of life, is simply illuminated by the example of life reality. The fact that even small things in life are of great importance is the basis of the composition of the work. The last leaf, which reached the level of the title of the work, was able to change a person's imaginary world, his outlook on life. The author immerses his ideological and artistic intention in this small artistic detail and promotes the great philosophy of life through it. Berman, who is the protagonist in the play is a generalization of the image of a number of western artists. Berman, who is in his sixties and has been creating for forty years but has not had much success in creating royal works, makes a living as an artist for artists who have not been able to become professionals. The period has left its mark on the psyche of the artist, who is "addicted to alcohol", "does not hate kind people" and considers himself a "guard dog" who protects two girls. Behind the image of a man who had become an evil man because of constant inadequacies and failures, stood a kind, good man. Both the image and the work of the artist are similar to the situation of the artists of that period. Downstairs, in a dimly lit room with the scent of black spruce, easel images that have been waiting for lines of the royal work for twenty-five years give a fuller picture of the artist. At the end of the work, it becomes clear that Berman, who hid his true nature - kindness, kindness behind fake shouts - is an impressive true creative person. Poverty, hardships and misfortunes did not break the heart of the creative artist. Berman, tears welling up in Johnson's mood, hides his feelings behind such rudeness. In the dialogues, Bermann's speech is full of meaning. In other words, behind the rebuke speech in girls, there is compassion and humanity. The last leaf to withstand wind, hail, and rain is Berman's masterpiece. This small work, created at the end of his life, brought a person back to life, and probably in this way, the creation of great works

of art began. The creation of a masterpiece is, in a sense, the end of an artist's life as a creator. From the reader's point of view, Berman achieved his dream. It is not clear whether the artist understood it or not. In conclusion, sometimes the character of the artist, sometimes portrayed as the main character, plays an important role in expressing the ideological and artistic intentions of the author. Through complex monologues, dialogues, interior and landscape images, the author's complex and delicate character is deeply expressed. Landscape and interior, which are the means of composition, play an important role in the deep expression of the artist's spiritual world, in symbolic and figurative interpretations, in accurately depicting the place where reality takes place.

The used literature:

1. Sulstonova M. "The art of Scenery" T., "Subject", 1983.
2. Miliyev S. "Poetics of global scientific and artistic interpretation." philol.f.d. diss. Avtoref
3. O'Henry. Last leaf. www.ziyo.uz.
4. Kuronov D, Mamajonov Z, Sheraliyeva M. The Literature dictionary. T. Academic publication, 2010.

